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The Chronicles of Callousness as Represented in Mia Couto's *The War of the Clowns*

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Abstract

This article investigates how callousness is reflected in Mia Couto's flash fiction entitled The War of the Clowns. Being callous is effortless since it stops empathizing with people or their feelings. The War of the Clowns is a flash fiction that tells two clowns who are always on banter with each other. They do not pay much attention to people around them, all they do is fight and insult one another every day and it progressively turns worse. Through qualitative method and explorative approach, this paper explores how callousness also reflects lack of emotions between the clowns and everyone in the cities. It is eerie how the fighting of two clowns could spread to the slaughter of the whole city. In conclusion, Couto's story shows that callousness is the worst aspect of being in ignorance which could easily bring anger and even destruction to wider societies.

Keywords *Callousness, Lack of Emotion, Mia Couto, War of the Clowns*

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INTRODUCTION

Literature is a collection of written literary works or it could also be referred to as any writing that is considered as an art. There are a lot of types of literary works, the most common ones that people know are prose, poetry, drama, journals, and novels, there are also a lot more including digital or even printed (Akbar et al., 2023; Docherty et al., 2023). One of the others is flash fiction. Flash fiction also known as microfiction is a literary work that is shorter than a novel, usually ranging from five to 1.000 words. Unlike a novel that tells the details of the story, flash fiction lets the reader infer and interpret the meaning of the story by themselves. A lot of writers can show the greatness of their story from the beginning to the end. They are keeping the readers entertained with the interesting plot and backstory (Akbar et al., 2023; Docherty et al., 2023). Like the story of *War of The Clowns* by Mia Couto that shows how the story keeps the readers questioning the plot, the characters, and the ending.

Callousness is the emotional trait that someone has who shows no sympathy toward other people's feelings (Brislin & Patrick, 2019; Meehan, 2019). They feel disengaged from their surroundings and do not feel the need to pay a slight bit of attention because of their insensitivity. In the story of *War of The Clowns* by Mia Couto, the characters show this kind of trait. It is shown in the way they act toward the surroundings and the people (Brislin & Patrick, 2019; Couto, 2014).

In the story, the two clowns are doing anything that they want without giving care to the others, but signs of callousness can also be seen in the people (Brislin & Patrick, 2019; Couto, 2014). Some of them are curious and pay attention to the clowns' actions but some also do not care about it until it affects them. At first, the clowns show their funny side showing no harm to the people and expressing themselves in a friendly manner. Although there are not a lot of people paying attention, some people feel attracted to them and feel the need to engage themselves (Brislin & Patrick, 2019; Couto, 2014). People were too busy with their own business to care about someone else, which shows that as long as it does not bother them or affect them in any kind of way, they would give any slight attention.

However, later on in the story, the clowns show changes in their actions and behaviour. It progressively becomes worse. They became more aggressive toward each other until it hit someone else (Couto, 2014; Meehan, 2019). They do not just attract a few of the pedestrians. Almost all the

people are watching this bizarre scene. Their action becomes noticeable. And people seem to finally notice this might be just the right entertainment that the people wanted; this is the one that they wanted. They thought this was the one that was worth their attention to stop by and watch. It piqued their attention. Some of the others stopped their mid-walking because they were concerned since it was affecting them (Couto, 2014; Listyaningsih et al., 2022). This scene continues for some time until it turns into more madness, and everyone is engaged. They are fighting each other with all their guts. They do not even know what they are fighting for, the only reason to keep going is to get back, to get revenge. That is the only thing in their head, all of them only care about themselves (Bamvita et al., 2021; Couto, 2014). There was no sympathy, empathy, or humanity present around them. They were selfish, ignorant, and totally callous.

Regarding the background above, this paper would like to find out the preservations of callousness in *The War of the Clowns*. People do not care for the clowns at first, but then it spreads to callousness among themselves. It keeps playing until the whole city is dead but no one really knows who did it first (Bamvita et al., 2021; Couto, 2014). By indicating the theory of callousness in matters of psychological levels, this paper examines how the story is not merely about the clowns, but also the people's reactions towards them and their own surroundings as well.

METHOD

To answer the questions in this paper, qualitative method is used to analyze specific document data. This discussion uses online and offline scripts to illustrate the relationship between Mia Couto's *War of The Clowns* and the theme of callousness. Data analysis involves obtaining sources, reading them carefully, comparing them to other subjects, citing them in the paper, and creating a reference list. The research data comes from both Mia Couto's short story and arguments about callousness. Each is read and broken down into individual elements. The plot and setting of a short story are primarily compared to the assumptions and logics used in callousness. The following analysis then focuses on how insensitive the characters are perceived to be in Mia Couto's short story. The subject here is a short story by Mia Couto, and the concept of callousness is a tool for its analysis. In addition, a detailed explanation of the widening analysis is also provided.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Contagious Deed of the Clowns to the People

War of The Clowns is a short story by Mia Couto in 2014 that tells about two clowns. These two have been arguing with each other (Couto, 2014). It seems like friendly fighting that the people around do not pay much attention to. The people only thought that it was normal because that is the clown's job, to act foolish, to entertain people. However, it was not much of an entertainment since they thought it was a nonsense argument between the clowns. It was not something that was worth enough of their attention (Bamvita et al., 2021; Couto, 2014). It starts from trivial things but ends as such an eerie situation. The proofs are listed as follows.

“—What's that? They asked”
 “—Why? It's only two clowns arguing”
Who could take them seriously? Ridiculous, the two comedians reparted. The arguments were common nonsense, the theme was a ninnery. And an entire day passed.” (Couto, 2014)

In those lines, it is shown that the people look down at them. They think those clowns were arguing to attract an audience but it was not interesting enough for them to pay attention. And it is also shown that even if no one gives attention to them, the clowns also could not care less. They keep on going with their banter and do not give any care to their surroundings (Couto, 2014; Hyde et al., 2013).

“The following morning, the two remained, obnoxious and outdoing each other. It seemed as though, between them, even yucca soured. In the street, meanwhile, those present were exhilarated with the masquerade. The buffoons began worsening their insults with fine-edged and finetuned barbs. Believing it to be a show, the passersby

left coins along the roadside. On the third day, however, the clowns arrived at acts of force. Their blows became a disarray, their counterkicks zinged more across air than across bodies. The children rollicked, imitating each jester's blows. And they laughed at the two fools, their bodies tripping upon their own selves." (Couto, 2014)

And after a while, their arguments worsened. They become more aggressive toward each other, throwing insults and offending each other. They still do not care about the people and the surroundings. But people started to pay attention, believing that it was a part of their performance to entertain people (Couto, 2014; Hyde et al., 2013). Some of them left coins to show their appreciation, feeling entertained by the whole show that they put on. Even the children feel excited to see the clowns arguing with each other. They tried to mimic them, throwing punches and kicks everywhere. They were amused, laughing (Couto, 2014; Hyde et al., 2013).

"—Dad, give me some coins to leave on the sidewalk" (Couto, 2014)

In that quotation, it shows how the children also feel entertained just like other passersby who left a coin. To show gratitude to the clowns, they feel the need to repay them after making them feel happy with their goofy act (Couto, 2014; Hyde et al., 2013). This unintentionally shows that those kids and some of the others are kind-hearted souls, they care enough to stop and give the clowns their attention even a penny. Even if they were not obligated to care or repay what the clowns did for them, it was still a nice gesture that made them different from the others (Couto, 2014; Hyde et al., 2013). This was not the case if later on in the story, the others are still minding their business.

"On the fourth day, the jabs and blows grew worse. Beneath their makeup, the faces of the clowns began to bleed. Some kids became scared. Was that true blood? In failures of trajectory, some were struck by directionless wallops. But it was light fare, only serving to add to the laughs. More and more people joined the gallery."
(Couto, 2014)

On the fourth day, they are still there. The clowns are continuing their activity from before. Worse than yesterday, they do not hold back with their punches. It does not even seem like friendly banter anymore, the two of them are bleeding. It made the people around them question whether it was real blood or just a fake one (Couto, 2014; Hawes et al., 2017). The children are terrified, and no longer feel amused. They do not feel joy seeing the ruthless scene in front of them. They shuddered in horror, this was not the clown from yesterday, they think. These clowns were totally different people from before, they believed (Couto, 2014; Hawes et al., 2017).

"—It's not serious, don't fret" (Couto, 2014)

That line was the parents trying to calm down their child. The parents still believed it was part of the show, this was planned. Those were fake blood and those jabs were not hurtful at all. Other people who watch alongside them also believe so (Couto, 2014; Listyaningsih et al., 2022). Other pedestrians decided to watch them too. This is it. This is the kind of entertainment that they are talking about, this is what they call entertaining. People were curious, their attention was piqued (Couto, 2014; Dotterer et al., 2020; Winiarski et al., 2018). They did not seem to care if those clowns were hurting each other, they just believed this was all under control. As long as they are not affected or feel disadvantaged by this, it is fine.

"—What's going on?"

Nothing. A friendly unsettling of accounts. It's not worth separating them. They'll tire out, it's nothing more than a bit of clowning around." (Couto, 2014)

That quotation indicates more people are interested, asking the other witnesses what is happening which is later answered by the others, it was nothing. The clowns will eventually stop because of tiredness. There is nothing to be concerned about. They are just acting silly and being goofy, this has happened before anyway (Couto, 2014; Winiarski et al., 2018). Believing that nothing unusual is happening, they go on with their day like no one is hurt, nothing happened.

“On the fifth day, however, one of the clowns armed himself with a stick. Advancing on his adversary, he discharged a blow that tore off his wig. The other, furious, equipped himself with a symmetrical beating bat and responded with the same dismeasure. The wooden rods whistled through the air in somersaults and deliriums. One of the spectators, unexpectedly, was struck. The man fell, deadspread.” (Couto, 2014)

On the fifth day, people might think it could not get worse than the whole rumbling yesterday, right? Wrong. One of the clowns now defends himself by carrying a stick. Attacking his opponent fiercely and rapidly. The other clown does not want to lose. Trying to match him by returning the blow from his enemy with the same energy. He swings his bat furiously. The situation is so chaotic, that everything turns into disarray (Bjørnebekk & Kjølbi, 2017; Couto, 2014). The clowns only care about themselves, they do not think much of others, whether their actions will affect or endanger them. The people who watched are shocked, concerned, and intrigued, all of the feelings become one. And finally, as the last blow, one person falls and becomes their first victim (Bjørnebekk & Kjølbi, 2017; Couto, 2014).

“A certain confusion arose, the souls divided. Little by little, two battlefields began to form. Various groups traded drubbings. Still more were felled. It entered a second week and the surrounding neighborhoods heard it said that a dizzied pandemonium had set in around the two clowns. And the thing embroiled the entire plaza. And the neighbors found it funny. Some went to the plaza to verify the reports. They returned with contradicting and inflamed versions of their own. The neighborhood continued to divide itself, in opposing opinions. Conflicts began in some neighborhoods.” (Couto, 2014)

A lot of people are confused about what is happening. They started questioning which one was right and who they should believe. They started to form groups which have different opinions and exchanged them with one another. A lot to uncover yet no answer (Bjørnebekk & Kjølbi, 2017; Couto, 2014). Entering a second week, the news about the clowns going for each other's throats is increasingly widespread. Some people still find it funny, brushing it off as if it were just the clowns' antics. Some of them even go out of their way to check out what is happening and see it for themselves. Going back, each person brings a different story, a version of their own (Bjørnebekk & Kjølbi, 2017; Couto, 2014). The people continue to divide themselves, confident in their opinions until conflicts start to arise.

“On the twentieth day, shots began to be heard. No one knew exactly where they came from. Could have been from any point in the city. Full of terror, the inhabitants armed themselves. The tiniest movement seemed suspect. The shots spread. Dead bodies began to accumulate in the streets. Terror reigned over the whole city. Soon, massacres began.” (Couto, 2014)

On the twentieth day, the peak of the clowns' event happened. A gunshot can be heard although no one knows where the sound is coming. Everyone was running around, the city was in panic. At this point, everyone was trying to save themselves, not caring for each other (Bjørnebekk & Kjølbi, 2017; Couto, 2014). They do not even try to extinguish the situation or even wonder what was the reason for them fighting. It was just anger and rage that were controlling them. No more love and sympathy. Everyone is selfish and ignorant towards each other, including the clowns. Making the smallest movement is not even possible, they will suspect each other (Bjørnebekk & Kjølbi, 2017; Couto, 2014). The shots spread more and faster, people were toppled. Everyone killed each other ruthlessly until no more left. This just shows how cruel and selfish humans can be, not showing empathy even to their kind. The clowns did not have to do anything in the end, they were the ones who killed each other because they were callous, and lacked empathy (Bjørnebekk & Kjølbi, 2017; Couto, 2014; Dotterer et al., 2020).

“At the beginning of the month, all the city's inhabitants had died. All except the two clowns. That morning, the comics sat, each one in his corner, and ridded themselves

of their ridiculous dress. They looked at each other, worn out. Later, they rose to their feet and embraced, laughing at the flags dispersed. Arm in arm, they gathered the coins from the roadsides. Together they crossed the city destroyed, careful not to tread on the cadavers. And they went in search of another city.” (Couto, 2014)

On the first day of the next month, all the people in the city had died, except for the two clowns. As if not guilty about the scene in front of them, the jesters get rid of their costumes. Standing up and looking at each other, feeling worn out. Guaranteed, they did not feel any remorse, sadness, or sorry about their action (Couto, 2014; Dotterer et al., 2020; Jansen et al., 2022). They look almost a little too proud. Embracing and laughing as they all the coins and pennies that scattered around the road. Carefully walking, not wanting to tread on the cadavers. They left the city, letting it die slowly to find another city. This might become another one of their achievements rather than sin (Couto, 2014; Listyaningsih et al., 2022).

Callousness as Psychological Traits

Being callous is actually so rational and humane. It is closely related to matters of ignorance and indifferentness. People used to do that since they have several trivial reasons. Those are used to be their individual reasons rather than the public ones (Anderson & Marcus, 2018; Blain et al., 2021; Dotterer et al., 2020). Many people think they get busy many times. It could confuse them more if they get involved in others' matters of life. they get trapped in many aspects to be done and even thought about. Matters of time become the one that makes them unable to meddle in other people's affairs. Even some people would like to do things on their own. It is related to being a perfectionist, but everyone even has little desire for that (Anderson & Marcus, 2018; Blain et al., 2021; Dotterer et al., 2020). In many events, it does not mean they never want to socialize, but there are also people who like and are comfortable doing anything by themselves.

On another matter, being ignorant is such a response from any experience in the past. Later, even callousness is not coincidental, but also socially constructed (Anderson & Marcus, 2018; Blain et al., 2021; Dotterer et al., 2020). In the past, ignorant people ever experienced disappointment when having a relationship with others. That is why people in this sense try to distance themselves from others. Furthermore, the ignorance is also since these people would like to have high expectations in many things. It is better for them to do anything alone. If it is good, then it is their achievements. If it is bad, let them take the responsibilities of it. It is due to the feeling that they are more capable than the others and even think that spending time with someone is tiring (Bamvita et al., 2020; Bjernebekk & Kjobi, 2016; Dotterer et al., 2020). It could be egotistical, but it is rational since there are many others who think similarly. They are not cruel, they are only different.

Furthermore, callousness could be more than the understandings above. It is a personality trait where people show no sign of sensitivity, empathy, lack of guilt, or remorse. It could also be a sense of low morale. People who have this trait usually tend to have antisocial behavior. This trait is associated with abnormalities in processing emotional feelings and decreasing their ability to react emotionally (Salsabila et al., 2022; Winiarski et al., 2018). Callousness itself is related to the early life stress that might happen to the child. However, callousness is one of the traits that has a connection to psychotic and criminal behavior including manipulation and exploitation if done by adolescents. A callous person shows cognitive and affective characteristics distinctively and also a particularly severe, aggressive antisocial behavior, this might start from youth going to adulthood. Especially children high in callousness, their attention is reduced when processing emotional faces (Winiarski et al., 2018; Brislin & Patrick, 2019).

Callousness can be identified from early childhood, and callous-unemotional are correlated to late preschool periods. Children with high callousness also have lower self-esteem, social support, and peer functioning (Annasai, et al. 2024; Meehan et al., 2019). This is a good time for parents to start early prevention and intervention that includes both giving recognition to their emotions and training them in emotion recognition. Socio-affective skills are greatly impacted to reduce or lessen the risk of callous-unemotional traits (Hyde et al., 2013; Meehan et al., 2019). What happens to the children, if being untreated, may also be realized in adulthood. Therefore, social skills to understand more people are always needed.

Consideration and empathy are two essential factors that facilitate humans in establishing and upholding their intimate connections. Individuals who lack compassion are likely to be deficient in these attributes, as they have failed to acquire them during their formative years (Annasai, et al. 2024; Dotterer et al., 2020; Meehan et al., 2019). Their lack of exposure to such experiences during childhood makes it more convenient for them to adopt an apathetic, indifferent, and ignorant demeanor towards others in adulthood. The origins of this behavior can stem from various sources, such as familial upbringing, friendship dynamics, or even the surrounding environment (Ackermann et al., 2019; Wirnoto et al., 2023).

The absence of affection and love within their family, the presence of negative friendships or the absence of close relations altogether, leads them to perceive the concept of emotional connection as peculiar and unfamiliar (Ackermann et al., 2019; Wirnoto et al., 2023). Furthermore, the absence of social and emotional support within their surroundings perpetuates this pattern, exerting a lasting influence from adolescence to adulthood, with increasingly detrimental consequences. In fact, callousness can manifest as aggression, which in turn escalates into psychosis, ultimately culminating in criminal behavior (Ackermann et al., 2019; Dotterer et al., 2020; Wirnoto et al., 2023).

Callousness is considered to play a big part in psychopathic personality because a sadistic person is most likely to be callous, although callous people may not always be sadistic. It is since a sadistic person could not care less about being a cold-hearted person (Anderson & Marcus, 2018; Blain et al., 2021). It is easy for them to be mean, to be cruel to others without feeling sorry or guilty about it. People with high sadism even enjoy watching others suffer. This gives them some kind of satisfaction as seen in the matters of dark tetrad. Callousness causes them to detach the feeling of empathy, affecting how they act which later on contributes to them being aggressive (Anderson & Marcus, 2018; Blain et al., 2021; Dotterer et al., 2020).

Adult psychopathy has a higher risk of re-offending and has proven to be difficult to be treated. That is why preventive intervention should be done specifically during the early stages of youth targets (Anderson & Marcus, 2018; Blain et al., 2021; Dotterer et al., 2020). Because as they grow older, those traits also grow constantly with them to more severe levels. And if this happens, it will be hard to prevent or even eliminate those traits. Although these things can be prevented, they have to be prevented from the early stages and they once again need help from other people (Anderson & Marcus, 2018; Dotterer et al., 2020; Hawes et al., 2016).

Problem-solving, discipline, encouragement, and positive participation are needed rather than yelling, talking in a high-pitched voice, and showing dominance (Bjornebekk & Kjobi, 2016; Dotterer et al., 2020). A higher level of positivity by giving intimacy and support will help people decrease their level of callous-unemotional traits. Anyone who builds up their ability to numb their feelings or just ignore their feelings such as sadness, fear, and anxiety also play a role in increasing their level of callous-unemotional traits (Bjornebekk & Kjobi, 2016; Dotterer et al., 2020).

Callous persons are also identified by several factors. They used to have deceitful interpersonal impression management. Their personalities also reflect a pretentious sense of self-worth and manipulation (Bjornebekk & Kjobi, 2016; Dotterer et al., 2020). It goes from lack of empathy towards failure to require responsibility. In this case, these people fail to answer what other people really need. It is common for them to be called as free riders. They have such parasitic orientation, lack of goals, impulsivity, and even abundant untrustworthiness (Bamvita et al., 2020; Bjornebekk & Kjobi, 2016; Dotterer et al., 2020).

The Chronicles of the Ignorant Clowns among Indifferent People

The flash fiction by *Mia Couto*, entitled *War of The Clowns* tells about a story of two psychopathic clowns who are currently in town. They spend most of their time either in a plaza or on the roadside acting goofy with each other (Couto, 2014; Dotterer et al., 2020; Nazir & Rashid, 2020). People around did not seem to care so much about them, so did the clowns. In the very first week, there was not much of an interaction between these two parties, both feeling disengaged. Some would stop and wonder what these two clowns were doing. But again, people thought it was just a clown they were just acting silly to get a penny. It is almost like looking down and underestimating the two clowns (Couto, 2014; Dotterer et al., 2020; Nazir & Rashid, 2020). People would pass by quickly as if having no sympathy.

On the next day though, the jesters started to insult each other, calling each other slurs, and throwing mockery. This attracted some of the passersby, they see this as some kind of entertainment. Without asking or knowing whether it was part of their show or not, they believed it was in an instant. Again, they are just clowns that is what they do. This shows a sign for both the clown and the people how they have no sensitivity and callousness (Akbar et al., 2023; Couto, 2014; Docherty et al., 2023). The clowns did not care to argue in a public place, knowing that it might attract bigger problems, while the people could not care enough to ask what happened, to stop the argument, to ask whether they are okay or not. The people only care about themselves, they see it as a comedy, and they feel entertained. That is the only reason they are starting to pay attention to the clowns (Couto, 2014; Dotterer et al., 2020; Nazir & Rashid, 2020).

Days passed again, the clowns' act changed drastically. So did the people. Their insults turn into punches. The audience is starting to add up, more people are roaming to watch them fighting (Anderson & Marcus, 2018; Couto, 2014). It is almost like they feel satisfaction seeing those two get hurt because of each other. Not even remorse or pity for them. No one stops them. People with a sadist characteristic does not feel any empathy at all to the other, sadistic person even finds it enjoyable to torture and see someone being tortured (Anderson & Marcus, 2018; Couto, 2014). The people only watch them as they ruthlessly beat each other. The clowns themselves show a very aggressive behavior, callousness making it hard for them to control their outrage (Anderson & Marcus, 2018; Bamvita et al., 2020; Couto, 2014).

The kids at first found this amusing, they thought the jesters were joking around. This shows the early stages that later on might impact them towards callousness. The environment and the people that surround them are people who are callous, with no empathy towards each other (Bjørnebekk & Kjøbli, 2017; Couto, 2014; Dotterer et al., 2020). Only harsh behavior that is being represented and exposed around their space. Then later on, they told their parents it's getting scarier. They feel terrified because it does not seem like the jesters were joking anymore. The parents who should validate their child's feelings (Bjørnebekk & Kjøbli, 2017; Couto, 2014; Dotterer et al., 2020). They just brushed them off, saying it was nothing serious. This could lead to an abandonment of the child's feeling, making them ignore it and numb it out. This could impact the children to have callous-unemotional traits later as they grow from adolescence to adulthood (Bjørnebekk & Kjøbli, 2017; Couto, 2014; Dotterer et al., 2020).

Indeed, it is interesting to see how Couto integrates time setting regarding any passing event in the story. The story is full of callousness though it is more prevalent to kids. It takes quite a long time until people realize that the terror is already intact (Dewangga et al., 2024; Obradovic et al., 2007). As the terror comes, callousness has been already normalized and people could no longer escape from it. They understand the conflicts only when the impacts are quite real for them. It reflects that terror is such reality but never be seen as a potential threat. Furthermore, the normalization is also part of callousness itself that shapes the matter of development of terror in this story (Dewangga et al., 2024; Obradovic et al., 2007). The more people ignore their surroundings, the more terror is unknown and easily erupts into such violence afterwards.

As the day went by, so did the action from the clowns. This time they even brought a property with them, arming themselves with a weapon to finish off each other. One of the clowns bought a stick and the other brought a bat. They both swing it at each other hoping it would injure one of them. They show a big sign of callousness here, their psychopathic action could be harmful to the others around them, but they did not care (Anderson & Marcus, 2018; Couto, 2014; Grabow & Becker-Blease, 2023). Psychopaths do not have any empathy left in them because they are callous. They kept on going until one of the audiences unexpectedly struck them until he fell. This creates confusion around the other audience, and spreads even confusing news to one another. This just makes the situation worse. Instead of uniting and trying to defuse the situation, they decided to split up and arrange groups with different opinions (Anderson & Marcus, 2018; Couto, 2014; Grabow & Becker-Blease, 2023). Conflicts begin between the people, without anyone trying to mediate each party, this will not be solved easily. Because they only care about themselves, their own opinion.

Almost at the end of the month, everything and everyone is in a disarray. They heard a shot but knew nothing about the location. It made them panic and run around like a maniac (Anderson & Marcus, 2018; Couto, 2014; Grabow & Becker-Blease, 2023). Suddenly everyone was against each

other. Suspecting every movement that someone makes, each of the inhabitants beat each other as their way to defend themselves. The shots spread more widely. Everyone is being aggressive and cruel towards each other, callousness takes over. No more sympathy, empathy, even humanity. No more of it (Annasai et al., 2024; Couto, 2014; Grabow & Becker-Blease, 2023). All of them have no pity for each other. The clowns, they obviously did not try to stop this situation. They feel pleased, seeing the horror scene in front of them. Psychopaths who have no remorse and are full of callousness letting the people in town die in each other's hands.

The above part is the reflection of interpersonal callousness in which uncaring and cold attitude arise among people (Feilhauer et al., 2013; Wijaya et al., 2024). They no longer regard others as human beings. Indeed, this aspect is the prolonging process of dehumanization and even demonization. Otherness must be destroyed in order to show the ultimate matters of self. Since people were children, any fight is intact but not deadly. When it becomes deadly, the sign of dangers is already ignored and callousness is more conditioned either (Feilhauer et al., 2013; Wijaya et al., 2024). In this story, people start to mimic what the clowns do but never realizes that even they have potential conflicts in between. Then, it becomes worse until it wipes out the entire city in general.

The way Couto states about pandemonium is also interesting. On this part, it is clear from the diction that the whole situation is spiraling into chaos. Words like pandemonium that reflect such a state of extreme confusion and disorder is not commonly used by writers unless it is to show how extreme it is. Writers tend to try to balance between functional and aesthetic parts of such words being used. Even with such extremities, the fact that they find it funny is concerning. It means more than violence. It accentuates more to high degree of callousness because people in this story do not interpret fear well and choose the wrong reaction to it instead. They are logical enough to check the scene but are so callous that they do not anything to break off the fight (Smarandreetha & Pasopati, 2024; Wijaya et al., 2024). It seems that some of them know that it is best to stop this fight but decide not to do anything and just argue about it. People with higher levels of callousness showed less reaction to scared faces and were not as good at recognizing when someone looks scared, which suggests they have a hard time understanding or feeling others' fear (Feilhauer et al., 2013; Smarandreetha & Pasopati, 2024). This is why people do not look for solution, callous people are wired not to see fear that is brewing in the vicinity.

At the very last, a new beginning for the clowns. What had just happened was already in the past. They feel content, no remorse or guilt that clinging on to them. It was ecstatic for them (Annasai et al., 2024; Couto, 2014; Grabow & Becker-Blease, 2023). Dead bodies scattered around the roadsides alongside some coins and pennies beside them. They get up and get rid of their ridiculous costumes. Embracing and laughing with each other as if they have no feelings towards all their victims (Couto, 2014; Grabow & Becker-Blease, 2023; Salsabila et al., 2023). Together walking slowly, they picked up the coins as they left the city, in search of another. The jesters technically do not have anything to do with the people dying. They are all the reason for their own death. There was no empathy that was present. They felt indifferent towards each other (Couto, 2014; Grabow & Becker-Blease, 2023; Salsabila et al., 2023).

The clowns might be the reason to start all the madness but it was just to trigger the people themselves, that finally clicks for them that it was easy. It was not hard for them to be mean, harsh, and hurt each other as their callousness took over (Couto, 2014; Grabow & Becker-Blease, 2023; Salsabila et al., 2023). But even so, the biggest signs of callousness are found in the clowns' behavior. They also had no hard time indirectly killing off the people. This callous behavior in an adult is no longer easy to prevent, because this trait is usually assessed through their adolescence. Reaching adulthood, it just becomes severe, it is not just aggression no more, it is more than that. Any callousness could always come to harming people and then becoming a threat for others (Couto, 2014; Hawes et al., 2016; Salsabila et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION

The conclusion from the ideas above is, psychopath behaviour in the story of *The War of the Clowns* is led by the clowns' callousness and lack of empathy that continues from their adolescence. Callousness starts from the things that people thought were small, such as lying and having not enough social interaction, acting harsh and rough in front of the kids. Those little things can

eventually become big if it were not being prevented. The kids in the story are a great example on how someone can be callous through their environment. Being disregarded for their feelings, making them think it is okay to ignore their feelings, to be numb. That is one of the other ways to train children to be callous, to lack empathy, to look down on someone. Callousness is not something to be underestimated, it could turn into severe aggression that later on gets worse which is also related to psychotic behavior. That is why prevention and intervention are needed from an early age, either from the parents or school-based training. Because reaching adulthood, it is no longer efficient. Just like what the clowns and the people appeared to be. They were callous enough to kill each other. Not giving any kind of consideration, empathy, or pity. It is hard for them to control their anger.

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